

The origins and supply resilience of electronic nanomaterials in Europe

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Research Article

Keywords: raw materials, nanomaterials, origins, electronics, batteries, photovoltaics, supply chains, trade, scale up

Posted Date: May 9th, 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-6619913/v1>

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Additional Declarations: The authors declare no competing interests.

The origins and supply resilience of electronic nanomaterials in Europe

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ABSTRACT

The growing frequency of global crises, from trade wars to export restrictions to logistical disruptions, have undermined the assumption that raw materials can be easily acquired through global trade. While policies such as the Critical Raw Materials Act address industrial needs, ensuring the scalability of frontier nanotechnologies now requires prioritising resilient, locally sourced materials and developing a clear understanding of trade-offs between performance and certainty of access. However, the resilience of European access to the relevant nanomaterials and their precursors is not well understood. This work introduces a Europe-focused supply resilience metric, R_E , which scores elements from hydrogen to bismuth based on geographic sourcing and recycling input rates, with materials that are fully sourced outside Europe obtaining the lowest scores and those that are produced domestically receiving the highest. We then extend R_E to a comprehensive range of compounds used across electrical components, battery electrodes, and photovoltaic solar cells. By correlating supply resilience with performance metrics such as mobility or theoretical capacity, this framework helps identify Europe-sourced alternatives to imported materials and underscores the need to improve recycling streams to recapture elements that are fully imported.

Keywords

raw materials, nanomaterials, origins, electronics, batteries, photovoltaics, supply chains, trade, scale up

Introduction

The post-World War II era ushered in an unprecedented period of globalisation underpinned by international trade liberalisation, the outsourcing of manufacturing to low-cost labour regions, ultra-low shipping costs, and a relative absence of major conflict among world powers. Institutions such as the European Coal and Steel Community (ECSC)—the precursor to the European Union—were founded on the principle that economic interdependence would render war “not merely unthinkable, but materially impossible,” as articulated in the 1950 Schuman Declaration.¹ Yet today, the erratic approach of the United States to repatriate manufacturing, particularly from China, has resulted in a significant deterioration in trade relations that are unlikely to be repaired in the short term, resulting in various financial institutions now widely predicting a global recession.² In competitive export sectors where margins are thin, many businesses are unlikely to survive arbitrarily applied tariffs, high inflation, or a sustained loss of consumer purchasing power. Moreover, this disruption only adds to a number of significant supply chain crises over the past five years, caused variously by a pandemic,³ war,⁴ human error,⁵ aggressive cost cutting,⁶ and piracy.⁷

In an uncertain landscape, securing access to the raw materials at the heart of advanced technologies is emerging as a pressing challenge. Material selection has traditionally prioritised cost metrics such as abundance or performance metrics such as electronic mobility or theoretical charge storage capacity, as certainty of supply was rarely an issue. However, with the ignition of trade wars and persistence of conflict in regions critical to global supply lines, research strategies based on maximal self-reliance through the use of locally sourced materials will be critical to ensuring the scale up of new technologies. This will require a framework that correlates performance metrics not only with abundance, but also with secure and reliable access. For example, despite magnesium ranking as the seventh most abundant element in Earth’s crust, its global supply remains heavily concentrated: China produces 66% of the world’s magnesite ore and refines 90% of all magnesium.⁸ Such concentration dependencies are also well-known in the context of batteries, with half of the world’s cobalt located in Zambia and Congo, and 88% of the world’s lithium produced by China and Chile. Perhaps surprisingly, despite MoS₂ being among the most studied two-dimensional materials, there is currently no mine producing molybdenite in Europe. While the Malmbjerg Molybdenum Project is projected to meet 30% of Europe’s molybdenum demand,⁹ it is located in Greenland—a Danish territory the United States is openly seeking to acquire ‘by any means’¹⁰—further compounding supply pressures that began earlier with China’s revocation of export licences.¹¹ Without reliable access to the critical inputs required for nanotechnology- and advanced materials-driven innovation, Europe risks falling behind in key technologies that will drive the future of industry, energy, and healthcare, in addition to the closure of suppliers or inflated material costs resulting in difficulties in frontier research.

This Article addresses this gap by introducing a Europe-centric metric to quantify the supply resilience, R_E , of elements ranging from hydrogen to bismuth. By mapping Europe’s dependence on domestic versus non-European sources, this metric allocates elements a score between 0 and 100, with materials that are fully sourced outside Europe and have low or zero recycling input rates obtaining the lowest scores and materials that are produced domestically and can be recycled scoring highly. Importantly, taking an elemental approach allows us to combine R_E stoichiometrically to also generate a supply resilience score for compounds. We compute these metrics for a comprehensive range of electronic nanomaterials: including conductors, dielectrics, and semiconductors for electronic components; to anode and cathode materials for lithium-, sodium-, and potassium-ion batteries; and to a range of nanomaterials

for photovoltaic devices. The goal of this work is to identify the elements and compounds with significant supply resilience for Europe and create performance–supply resilience phase diagrams to strengthen European research directions. As the performance of enormous number of nanomaterials has now been investigated, the supply resilience metric serves as a critical tool for assessing the viability of scale-up in an era of geopolitical and economic uncertainty.

Elemental abundance and European reliance on imports

Over the past several decades, Europe's dependence on trade to acquire elements that are not domestically available has been relatively free of risk. The percentage of an element's supply that must be imported to meet demand is characterised by the import reliance, IR , relating how much Europe produces, exports, and imports, such that

$$IR = \frac{Imports - Exports}{Domestic\ production + (Imports - Exports)} \quad (1)$$

with negative values defaulting to 0%. Import reliance data are available from the Raw Materials Information System,¹² the Study on the Critical Raw Materials (CRM) for the EU (latest edition 2023),⁸ and factsheets produced by the SCRREEN3 network (Solutions for Critical Raw Materials-European Expert Network).¹³ While the CRM report produces a supply risk metric for critical raw materials, the focus of this paper is the elements themselves to allow us compute a resilience for a given compound.

Supplementary Note 1 lists the elements from hydrogen to bismuth with their respective primary mineralisation type and primary mineral. Many elements form native deposits, such as sulphur, gold, and silver, while others are extracted as by-products from processing primary ores. For example, the nuclear industry in France requires highly purified zirconium but the primary mineral, zircon ($ZrSiO_4$), contains about 1 part in 50 of hafnium, which is separated out in such quantities that Europe has become a net exporter. Similarly, many elements are only produced as by-products of Pb, Zn, and Cu processing, such as gallium, germanium, selenium, indium, tellurium, and bismuth, meaning that these elements can only be obtained by having access to the primary ore and the capability to process and separate out its components. In many cases, no primary deposits exist within Europe but, once imported, can be processed domestically, with an example being borates imported from Turkey and processed in Germany. The European Commission data for hydrogen and carbon normally refer to industrial-use liquid hydrogen and natural graphite—with an import reliance of 56% and 99%, respectively—but, for the purposes of a nanomaterial-based metric, we take H, C, O, and N to be easily sourced (e.g., from biomass, air or methane) with no import reliance. We note that this means organic materials, such as PEDOT:PSS, would be considered to have no import reliance despite being derived from petrochemical precursors, but we assume the supply of oil will be constant owing to its centrality in our society.

Figure 1a shows the import reliance for each element, from high to low (see Supplementary Note 2). Here, we use the EU and global end-of-life recycle input rate (RIR) to estimate the amount of material that would need to be imported should these recycling rates be achieved. To do this, we multiply the elemental import reliance by the fraction of material that cannot be recycled for the EU, $1 - RIR_{EU}$, and for the globe, $1 - RIR_{Global}$. The European recycling rate could reduce the import reliance for many of the fully imported materials (e.g., platinum group and rare-earth); however, in general, the recycling rates are much lower than global rates, where > 50% have been achieved in some cases. Figure 1a also highlights that

elements that are fully imported must be prioritised for recycling and recovery to reduce sole dependence on external sources.

Figure 1b plots the import reliance for each element against elemental abundance. This plot demonstrates the need for a metric beyond abundance as we find that Europe is completely reliant on imports for many of the most abundant elements. Iron (77%), magnesium (99%), silicon metal (as high purity elemental silicon is referred to) (60%), titanium metal (100%), and aluminium metal (89%) are all heavily imported. To meet the current needs of the continent, even elements such as copper and zinc, which are widely mined across Europe, are also partially imported. Figure 1c shows the largest fraction that is imported to the EU from a single country, f , against abundance as a measure of how concentrated the supply chain is. While a market share of 20% is considered concentrated in terms of competition, over 50% of the supply of 34 of the 72 elements surveyed here comes from a single country, with no relationship between abundance and diversity of suppliers.

Figure 1 | **Abundance and import reliance.** **a** | The import reliance for each element (filled circles). Hollow circles represent the import reliance times the fraction of an element that is not recycled (using the End-of-Life Recycling Input Rate for the EU). The hollow triangles represent the same but using the global EoL RIR. **b** | The import reliance for each element as a function of abundance. **c** | The fraction of the largest supplier for each element versus abundance.

Supply resilience: The elements

To navigate the uncertainty of current and future trade relationships, a strategy of maximal self-reliance for the sourcing of raw materials may be the safest way to guide frontier research. Based on the data in Figure 1a, we therefore propose a metric for quantifying the resilience of supply for a given element, considering both the import reliance and also the end-of-life recycling input rate, RIR . We define the supply resilience of a given element as

$$R_E = 100[1 - (IR(1 - RIR_{EU}))] \quad (2)$$

where IR here is the fractional import reliance (i.e., not percentage) and RIR_{EU} is the fractional recycling input rate for the EU (see Supplementary Note 2). With this equation, the more of an element is recycled and the less is imported, the more resilient we consider it against supply crises, with the metric varying between 0 (fully reliant on imports) and 100 (fully self-sufficient). We note that this work is only assessing access to material and does not consider the environmental impact in extraction, processability, or end of life.

Figure 2 | **Supply resilience and supplier concentration.** **a**, The supply resilience of each of the elements calculated with Eq. 1. Carbon has two entries; one for natural graphite (labelled) and one for carbon nanostructures grown using methane, for example. **b**, Largest supplier fraction for EU-sourced elements plotted against the supply resilience for that element. The blue data points represent when the largest supplier is from Europe, while the red data points represent when the largest supplier is from outside Europe. The country source of each element and the amount imported are highlighted.

We plot these data for each element in Figure 2a, where we designate elements with an $R_E > 80$ as being strongly resilient against supply shocks, while those with an $R_E < 20$ as being weakly resilient. We also summarise these data in the form of the periodic table in Table 1 to allow quick referencing of supply resilience, largest supplier fraction, cost, and chemical properties to aid decision-making for top-down and bottom-up nanomaterial synthesis techniques (Supplementary Note 3 contains the same table with abundance in place of cost). Europe is fully self-reliant in the chalcogens and two of the halides (F and Cl), and also sodium, calcium, and strontium. We note that while Europe is self-reliant in hafnium, it is a by-product of zircon as mentioned above, which is fully imported. Unsurprisingly, Europe is fully reliant on imports for rare-earth elements, platinum group metals, lithium, rubidium, and niobium, but also, surprisingly, for titanium, boron, iodine, and bromine. In the case of materials that are fully imported, Supplementary Note 2 also contains those European nations where deposits are known to exist, but are currently considered economically uninteresting.

While supply resilience highlights the extent of Europe's dependence on imports, the concentration of supply from single countries adds an additional layer of vulnerability—elements with both low resilience and high supplier concentration pose the greatest risk. Figure 2b shows the largest supplier fraction plotted against the supply resilience for each element, where we find those elements with the lowest supply resilience tend to have dominant suppliers from outside Europe. Of these, the least secure elements are rubidium, boron, magnesium, niobium, lithium, platinum group metals, and some lanthanides, with >79% of European needs being met with from a single country. An exception is strontium, where 99% of the European supply is produced in Spain. Elements on the bottom right of the graph tend to come from European countries, and with much higher diversity of sources. Europe is self-sufficient in metals such as gold, silver, tin, lead, cadmium, and indium, with each coming from a diverse number of sources. An exception here is tellurium, which, as a by-product of gold, lead, and copper mining, can be produced within Europe, so while 27% of European tellurium comes from Canada, eight other countries provide the remainder, with over 56% coming from inside the EU.

To compute the supply resilience of a compound, R_C , we use geometric mean of compound's stoichiometric R_E . Taking the example of a three-element compound with a chemical formula $A_aB_bC_c$, its supply resilience would be given by

$$R_C = \left((R_{E,A})^a (R_{E,B})^b (R_{E,C})^c \right)^{1/(a+b+c)} \quad (3)$$

where R_E is the supply resilience of a given element in the compound formula and the superscript refers to its stoichiometry. For example, Sb_2Te_2Se has $R_{E,A} = 28$, $R_{E,B} = 100$, $R_{E,C} = 98$, $a = 2$, $b = 2$, and $c = 1$, giving a supply resilience for the compound of $R_C = 60$. Using the geometric mean has several advantages: one, if any element has zero resilience (i.e., is fully imported from outside Europe), the compound has zero resilience; two, it is weighted via the number of atoms of a given element, meaning more atoms of a low resilience material will weight the compound lower; and three, it decreases with additional elements. The R_E for each element is listed in Supplementary Note 2, allowing the calculation of R_C for compounds not covered in this work (see Methods).

Table 1 | **The periodic table.** We visualise the supply resilience, largest supplier fraction, and approximate cost of each element, with all data available in Supplementary Notes 1 and 2. A version of this table with abundance in place of cost is available in Supplementary Note 3.

Supply resilience: Electronic components

Figure 3a shows the conductivity of various conductive nanomaterials versus their supply resilience (see Supplementary Note 4). Here, we use literature values for thin films deposited by any means, with the conductivities of bulk metals shown for reference. We consider MAX phase of the MXenes when calculating the supply resilience, with most clustering to the lower end of the resilience axis owing to components such as titanium, niobium, and vanadium. We note that Cr-Xenes and Hf-Xenes have yet to be synthesised¹⁴ but, if created, would vastly improve the supply resilience of the MXene. As organic materials, graphene and carbon nanotubes are highly resilient and easily synthesised, with conductivities in the range of 10^2 – 10^5 S m⁻¹ owing to variations at the inter-sheet and inter-tube junctions,¹⁵ with ITO and FTO also being strongly resilient. The conductivity of networks of gold and silver nanomaterials are shown in the indicated ranges, and are below the value for the bulk metals owing to imperfect sintering processes and the effect of porosity in the networks.

Considering dielectrics, Figure 3b shows the dielectric constant against supply resilience for a range of metal oxides, along with layered and polymeric materials (see Supplementary Note 5). Common materials, such as SiO₂ and Al₂O₃, have resiliences < 80 owing to the import of high purity silicon and aluminium. However, when it comes to highly scaled electronics where the dielectric interface is the key bottleneck for high performance channel materials, 2D insulators have emerged as potential candidates to address this.¹⁶ Boron nitride (BN) is perhaps the most studied 2D insulator; however, Europe is fully dependent on Türkiye for all of its boron. While HfO₂ is fully sourced within Europe and highly resilient, Hf's parent mineral, zircon, is fully imported, mostly from South Africa. The sheet silicates, such as montmorillonite (MMT), mica, talc, and kaolin, are both abundant and widely available with dielectric constants in a similar range, while fluor spar (CaF₂), with an ultra-wide bandgap of 12.1 eV, is 60% imported. Polymeric dielectrics, such as various types of cellulose, chitosan, and sodium alginate, have become important for printed electronics and are fully resilient owing to their sustainable and abundant origins, with hydration-dependent dielectric constants in the range of 5–40.¹⁷

To evaluate the supply resilience of semiconductors, we plot their charge carrier mobility for both single crystals—representing the maximum achievable values should grain boundaries or junctions not be an issue—and thin films, which reflect mobilities attained via scalable techniques like printing or chemical vapour deposition, as shown in Figures 3c and 3d, respectively, with a focus on two-dimensional semiconductors (see Supplementary Notes 6 and 7). Of the 336 semiconducting 2D materials with band gaps below 2.5 eV (see Methods), experimental mobility values were found for only 47, as shown in Figure 3c. These materials tend to cluster in the upper-right quadrant of the plot, with the highest scores observed for compounds combining a highly resilient metal (e.g., W, Sn, In, or Hf) with a chalcogen. Conversely, materials with elements like Pd, Ga, or black phosphorous (BP) are much less resilient despite having a high experimental mobility. Single-crystal organic materials tend to have maximum mobilities of ~ 50 (rubrene) owing to hopping transport but, as organic materials, can be synthesised within Europe. While silicon is among the highest single crystal mobilities, the European supply of purified silicon is mostly sourced from China. Of the metal oxides, the mobilities are reasonably similar across all compositions, with the tin-containing compounds with the strongest resilience. The highest mobilities are found in nanowires of the III–V semiconductors; however, only those that contain indium have strong supply resilience. To ensure the graph remains readable, we highlight separately that carbon nanotubes have

Figure 3d shows the mobility versus supply resilience for large-area films, where here we divide the 2D materials between nanosheet networks (2D films that have junctions between the nanosheets, i.e., solution processes) and thin films (2D films that have grain boundaries between the nanosheets, i.e., growth processes). Similar to Figure 3c, the most resilient materials are those containing tin, tungsten, and zinc, and also organics, with the supply resilience being reduced for those 2D materials that are doped with heavily imported elements, such as niobium or lanthanum. In all cases, the mobilities in Figure 3d are lower than those in Figure 3c owing to the parasitic resistances associated with junctions and grain boundaries,¹⁵ with 1D systems especially affected.

In addition, we also sought 2D materials where mobilities were theoretically calculated to provide guidance for future research. Here, we found slightly more materials: 120 n-type materials and 92 p-type as shown in Supplementary Note 8. These data provide a new method of down-selection for commercial exploitation as materials like InSe or SnSe can deliver mobilities comparable to PtSe₂ or black phosphorous, while being comparatively immune to supply chain crises and cost inflation, meaning Europe is well placed to develop these materials at scale.

Supply resilience: Battery materials

Next, we consider supply resilience in the context of electrode materials for lithium-ion batteries (LiBs) and related energy storage systems (see Supplementary Note 9). By considering the reactions between lithium ions and active materials within battery electrodes, it is possible to quantify the theoretical lithium storage capacity for each element.¹⁹ This theoretical capacity is plotted versus supply resilience in Figure 4a, illustrating a number of interesting points. Firstly, a number of reasonably high capacity elements have very high supply resilience, notably sulphur, which is likely to become important owing to the significant energy densities offered by lithium–sulphur batteries.^{20,21} However, the highest capacity elements, Si and P, have R_E values below 50%. In addition, silicon's low R_E is problematic given its status as the most promising future anode material, with most of the global supply of purified silicon coming from China (76% of the global supply). Moreover, the current most common anode material, graphite, has even lower supply resilience, again owing to the dominance of Chinese exports of spherical graphite (67% of the global supply). This graph also highlights the fact that lithium itself has a supply resilience of zero, meaning Europe can never sustain itself in LiB production.

Despite these high values, most electrode materials used in LiBs are compounds rather than elemental materials. As shown in Figure 4b, the theoretical capacity for a range of active material compounds commonly used in LiBs is plotted versus the compound supply resilience, R_C . Here we find that, broadly speaking, the higher capacity compounds have better supply resilience than those with lower capacity, noting that graphene has supply resilience of 100 owing to its diverse synthesis options compared to the current monopoly on naturally occurring spherical graphite. In addition, there are a number of materials suitable for use in both cathodes and anodes which have supply resilience above 60%, which is relatively positive for battery manufacturing in the EU. Of particular note here are the organic electrodes, which range from carbonyl or organo-sulphur compounds to conductive polymers and organic radicals.²² While most are produced from petrochemicals, some can be synthesised from biomass or bulk industrial chemicals, giving them a supply resilience of 100, albeit with generally lower theoretical capacities than inorganic materials.

Owing to lithium's cost, concentrated production, and environmentally-damaging extraction processes, it is likely that LiBs will eventually be replaced by sodium-ion batteries (NaIBs) and potassium-ion batteries (KIBs), especially in non-vehicle applications where gravimetric capacity is not critical. Indeed, we find that the R_E values for Na and K (100 and 67, respectively) to be considerably higher than that of Li. Figure 4c and 4d plots a range of anodes and cathodes for each ion type, with a range of resilience shown for both (see Supplementary Notes 10 and 11). While the highest capacity material, P, in both Figure 4c and 4d has a relatively low supply resilience for both NaIBs and KIBs, there is a broad cohort of inorganic cathode and anode materials that combine high capacity and high values of R_C . However, as with the LiBs, both NaIBs and KIBs have a broad range of organic materials available as cathodes, with well-known materials such as Prussian blue (and its analogues) and Vitamin K used in KIBs. Such materials again add significant supply resilience to their respective batteries, implying that beyond-lithium battery manufacturing in Europe should be quite resilient to supply shocks.

Figure 4 | **Batteries.** **a** | The theoretical capacity for each of the elements calculated for Li (references in Supplementary Note 9). **b** | The theoretical capacity for anodes and cathodes in lithium-ion batteries, including S form Li-S batteries (full list with references in Supplementary Note 9). **c** | Theoretical capacity of anodes and cathodes in sodium-ion batteries, where organic electrodes show the most resilience (full list with references in Supplementary Note 10). **d** | The theoretical capacity of anodes and cathodes in potassium-ion batteries (full list with references in Supplementary Note 11).

Supply resilience: Photovoltaics

Photovoltaics (PVs) are a key pillar of the global clean energy transition, but their supply chain is highly vulnerable. By the end of 2025, China is projected to control nearly 95% of global production of polysilicon, silicon ingots, and wafers for PV modules.²³ PV technologies are commonly categorised into three generations: the first is dominated by mature silicon-based cells; the second includes the thin-film technologies such as CdTe, copper–indium–gallium–selenide (CIGS), and amorphous silicon; and the third generation encompasses emerging PV technologies designed to surpass the efficiency limits of traditional cells. These include perovskites, along with dye-sensitised, organic, and ferroelectric solar cells, and also advanced materials like gallium arsenide (GaAs). In this section, we focus on the second and third generations, examining both the light-absorbing materials and the selective extraction materials used in n-i-p and p-i-n configurations shown in Figure 5a, which are core components of these cells.

Given the intense current research and investment in perovskite technology, Figure 5b and 5c shows the maximum reported power conversion efficiencies (PCE) for a range of hole and electron transport materials used in perovskite solar cells, respectively, across both n-i-p and p-i-n configurations (Supplementary Notes 12–15). These configurations impose restrictions on the kind of materials used: in a p-i-n solar cell, the hole transport material (HTM) must be transparent to allow light to pass, whereas in an n-i-p configuration, it can be opaque, but must be deposited from an anhydrous solvent that does not dissolve the perovskite.

We find that many of the top-performing HTMs are solely organic, contributing to high supply resilience. Materials such as P3HT, DM, and PTAA, in the n-i-p architecture, are 100% resilient, with the highest performing material Spiro-OMeTAD having zero resilience when mixed with lithium. In the p-i-n configuration, the leading HTM is Me-4PACz, whose performance is improved with the addition of NiO or 2PACz, while PTAA is the most resilient high-performance material. In contrast, the electron transport materials (ETMs) used in n-i-p structures are often metal oxides, valued for their stability, performance, and cost-effectiveness. Here, we find that the highest-performing material, SnO₂, is fully resilient, while TiO₂, the most widely used, has a lower supply resilience (~20) due to the high reliance on imports for titanium. For p-i-n devices, the dominant ETMs are fullerenes combined with SnO₂, which are again 100% resilient.

Figure 5d shows the supply resilience of the absorption layers for a range of photovoltaic technologies (see Supplementary Note 16), where it is immediately evident that this layer is the main supply-chain vulnerability for perovskite PV cells. High efficiency (>20%) perovskite cells require caesium and iodine, which is almost exclusively sourced from Chile (67%) and Japan (28%).²⁴ Europe has no known domestic sources of iodine, underscoring the importance of stable trade agreements to support the continent's growing perovskite start-up ecosystem. While iodine-free perovskites with significantly higher supply resilience have been reported, their power conversion efficiencies typically remain below 15%, limiting their competitiveness.

Figure 5 | **Photovoltaics.** **a** | Schematics of the types of photovoltaic cells considered in the main text. **b** | The power conversion efficiency of perovskite solar cells with the indicated hole transport layers for n-i-p (plain text) and p-i-n (in bold) configurations. A selection of data points is labelled, with the full list available in Supplementary Notes 12 and 13. **c** | The power conversion efficiency of perovskite cells containing the indicated electron transport layers, with n-i-p configurations indicated in plaintext and p-i-n configurations indicated in bold. An indicative selection of data points is labelled, with the full list available in Supplementary Notes 14 and 15. **d** | The supply resilience of a range of a range of light absorbing layers across several cell types. All references are available in Supplementary Note 16.

Thin-film technologies tend to have higher supply resilience, with highly resilient CdTe cells in the range of 15–23% efficiency, similar to organic-based cells. However, these materials present other challenges, such as cadmium being registered under REACH regulation due to its toxicity,²⁵ while organic photovoltaics face efficiency limitations associated with hopping transport mechanisms that may hinder large-scale investment. GaAs, as the record holder for

single-junction solar cells, scores high on efficiency but low on supply resilience owing to 69% of Europe's gallium being supplied by China. While dye-sensitised solar cells have begun to reach appreciable efficiencies, especially with co-sensitised cells, their reliance on TiO₂ nanoparticles reduces their supply resilience to the range of 50–60%. As the most nascent technology, ferroelectric solar cells have efficiencies < 10% but are competitive with iodine-free perovskites and Cu₂O thin films.

Conclusions & Outlook

The supply resilience metric introduced here offers a compound-level tool for consolidating performance with feasibility to complement EU policies such as the Critical Raw Materials Act. In addition, this analysis suggests several strategic questions:

- What constitutes an acceptable trade-off between material performance and supply resilience in the design and selection of nanomaterials for new technologies?
- Can hybrid materials be strategically engineered to combine high supply resilience elements in a way that functionally mimics the properties of materials reliant on low resilience elements?
- How will developing European elements affect carbon emissions (via new mining) and cost price (via improved labour conditions in the supply chains)?
- Should frontier materials research shift its focus from maximising performance to prioritising scalability under the constraints of material access and geopolitical risk?
- What policy and infrastructural changes are required to adapt Europe's recycling and circularity directives to prioritise elements for which no domestic primary sources exist?

In mapping R_E and R_C across a broad range of critical nanomaterials, we believe these metrics will allow more informed choices that balance high functionality with lower exposure to geopolitical risk, trade volatility, or cost instability. Crucially, this approach also supports the proactive identification of contingency materials during proposal development to ensure continuity in the event of supply disruptions or significant price fluctuations. It is becoming clear that high performance in advanced technologies will no longer be paid solely in cost, but also in certainty.

Methods

Supply resilience calculations

The elemental supply resilience values, R_E , were calculated using Eq. 2 and compound supply resilience, R_C , with Eq. 3 in the main text, both using the values in Supplementary Note 2. When calculating R_C for compounds with non-integer stoichiometric values, the resulting R_C value can exceed 100 (e.g., CdTe_{1-x}Se_x for $0 < x < 1$). We therefore round each stoichiometry in these elements to 1 to estimate R_C .

As many organic materials are non-stoichiometric, we cannot assign a compound supply resilience value using the same method. Instead, we take each element that is present in the compound and assign it a stoichiometric value of 1 and calculate R_C as above. For example, D18:L8-BO:B6Cl is used as an absorption layer in organic photovoltaic solar cells and is composed of the elements C, H, S, N, O, F, B, and Cl. We therefore calculate R_C as $(100 * 100 * 100 * 100 * 100 * 41 * 1 * 100)^{1/8} = 50$. Similarly, for inorganic non-stoichiometric compounds, such as NiO_x, we assign a value of $x = 1$.

Semiconductor selection process

To create a list of semiconducting 2D materials to search for, we extracted the 781 “easily exfoliable” materials from the Supplementary Information of the 2D Material Cloud Database²⁶ and sorted them by bandgap, classifying a semiconductor as having an $E_g < 2.5$ eV. This gave 336 materials for which we performed a literature review. We sought both experimentally measured and theoretical mobilities for each of these materials, with the full lists of materials we found values for in Supplementary Notes 6–8. The mobility values for these materials and the others in Figure 3c and 3d represent the highest values we could find for experimental measurements but note those we found may not be the highest reported values and, as such, can be interpreted as a sufficiently high value for the purposes of comparison.

Owing to the significant range of theoretically calculated mobility values, we imposed a cut-off of mobility values $>10,000 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ when computed using simple models (e.g., zero-temperature conditions or ignoring electron–phonon scattering).

Battery electrode selection process

For each battery type, we sought recent reviews that mention theoretical capacities for a range of both inorganic and organic electrodes. For inorganic electrodes, we sought values that were sufficiently different from each other to be visible on the graphs in Figure 4. For organic electrodes, we started with the highest and lowest theoretical capacities, and then included a selection of other materials within this range.

Perovskite selection process

The data in Figure 5b, 5c, and 5d were sourced from the Perovskite Database Project,²⁷ which compiles performance metrics of perovskite solar cells from publications dating back to 2013. For this analysis, we selected publications from 2015 to 2025, totalling approximately 43,000 entries. For each active layer, we selected the best-performing materials for analysis and presentation in Figure 5. The R_c values were calculated using the non-stoichiometric procedure above. The data for the other thin-film PV technologies in Figure 5d are based on the highest efficiency devices reported to date. The R_c values for the DSSCs in Figure 5d were calculated using the composition of the dye plus the TiO_2 nanoparticles.

Acknowledgements

AGK acknowledges funding from the European Commission through a Marie Skłodowska–Curie Postdoctoral Fellowship “NanoHarvest” (proposal number: 101107032). CG and JNC acknowledge funding from the European Union through the Horizon Europe project 2D-PRINTABLE (GA-101135196) and the Research Ireland funded Frontiers for the Future (Award) Project Number 215815. K.S. acknowledges financial support by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) through CRC-1415 – 417590517.

Author Contributions

CT performed background research, designed the figures, and co-wrote the paper. AGK and JNC created the metrics. CG performed background research and prepared the SI. KS and ZS performed background research. JNC, EF, RM, and LS provided analysis. AGK conceived the study, performed background research, parsed the data, designed the figures, and wrote the paper.

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

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